

1 **Calcium homeostasis associated with NLR induction.**

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8 NLRs have homeostatic functions across cell- and stimulus type. We demonstrate here a role for NLR in
9 sensing and signaling associated with calcium homeostasis in the cell. In cells expressing an *NLRC4*
10 variant bearing a specific point mutation (*NLRC4* T337S), significant alterations in general homeostasis
11 were evident (protein folding, thioredoxin, metallothionein homeostasis sensors) as well as biologically
12 important changes in calcium homeostasis. This included activation of calcium homeostasis modulator
13 family member 2, *CALHM2*. NLRs can regulate homeostasis broadly in the cell and in specific contexts
14 associated with immunologic signal transduction.

15 Citations

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